

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF THE CAUCHY PROBLEM
FOR IDEAL PLASTICITY EQUATIONS WITH YIELD
CONDITION DEPENDING ON THE AVERAGE STRESS**

Nguyen Minh Hue, Pham Thi Thuy,
Faculty of Basic Science,
Ho Chi Minh City University of Transport,
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Annotation: The Cauchy problem of the propagation of zones of a plastic state in an unbounded medium from the boundary of a convex surface, on which normal pressure, tangential forces, and given displacement velocities act, is considered. In the case of complete plasticity and linear dependence of the yield condition on the average stress, the system of quasi-static ideal plasticity equations describing the stress-strain state of the medium is hyperbolic. When solving this system numerically, a different scheme is used for hyperbolic systems of conservation laws.

Keywords: stress, deformation, full plasticity, yield strength, ideal plasticity, hyperbolic system

**ЧИСЛЕННОЕ РЕШЕНИЕ ЗАДАЧИ КОШИ ДЛЯ УРАВНЕНИЙ
ИДЕАЛЬНОЙ ПЛАСТИЧНОСТИ С УСЛОВИЕМ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ
В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ СРЕДНЕГО НАПРЯЖЕНИЯ.**

Нгуен Минь Хюэ, Фам Тхи Туи,
Факультет фундаментальных наук,
Университет транспорта Хошимина,
Хошимин, Вьетнам

Аннотация: Рассмотрена задача Коши о распространении зон пластического состояния в неограниченной среде от границы

выпуклой поверхности, на которую действуют нормальное давление, касательные силы и заданные скорости перемещений. В случае полной пластичности и линейной зависимости условия текучести от среднего напряжения система квазистатических уравнений идеальной пластичности, описывающая напряженно-деформированное состояние среды, является гиперболической. При численном решении этой системы для гиперболических систем законов сохранения используется другая схема.

Ключевые слова: напряжение, деформация, полная пластичность, предел текучести, идеальная пластичность, гиперболическая система

Quasi-static equations of ideal plasticity for determining stresses and displacement rates in the case of complete plasticity have the form:

$$\sigma_{ij,j} = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$\max(|\sigma_1 - \sigma_2|, |\sigma_2 - \sigma_3|, |\sigma_1 - \sigma_3|) = 2(k_s - m\sigma), \tag{2}$$

$$\sigma < k_s/m,$$

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_3, \tag{3}$$

$$e_{11} + e_{22} + e_{33} = 0, \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} e_{11} & e_{12} & e_{13} \\ e_{21} & e_{22} & e_{23} \\ e_{31} & e_{32} & e_{33} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_3 \end{bmatrix} = \lambda \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad 2e_{ij} = u_{i,j} + u_{j,i} \tag{5}$$

Here σ_{ij} are the components of the symmetric stress tensor in the Cartesian coordinate system x_1, x_2, x_3 ; $\sigma = \frac{(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})}{3}$ is the mean stress; $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are principal stresses; $k_s > 0, m > 0$ are constants; e_{ij} are the strain rate tensor components; u_i are the components of the displacement velocity vector; n_i are the components of the unit eigenvector of the stress tensor corresponding to the non-multiple eigenvalue (principal stress) σ_1 .

Equality (2) means a linear dependence of the maximum shear stress on the average pressure [1] (such a dependence (Fig. 1) is typical for some soils [2]). Equality (3) means the Haar–Karman completes plasticity condition [3], equality (4) is the incompressibility condition [4], and relation (5) is the isotropy condition [4].

Figure 1 – Physical and mechanical properties of sand under pressure

System (1)–(3) is studied using D. D. Ivlev's representation of the stress tensor in the form [4]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= \frac{\xi}{a} + \frac{k_s}{m} + \xi n_1^2, & \sigma_{12} &= \xi n_1 n_2, \\ \sigma_{22} &= \frac{\xi}{a} + \frac{k_s}{m} + \xi n_2^2, & \sigma_{13} &= \xi n_1 n_3, \\ \sigma_{33} &= \frac{\xi}{a} + \frac{k_s}{m} + \xi n_3^2, & \sigma_{23} &= \xi n_2 n_3,\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

$$\xi = 2\varepsilon(k_s - m\sigma) = 2\varepsilon e^{ap}, \quad a = \frac{-6m}{3\varepsilon + 2m}, \quad \varepsilon = \pm 1.$$

Substitution (6) identically satisfies relations (2), (3). In this case, the principal stresses are equal

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{4}{3}\varepsilon(k_s - m\sigma) + \sigma, \quad \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -\frac{2}{3}\varepsilon(k_s - m\sigma) + \sigma.$$

The functions p, n_1, n_2, n_3 depending on x_1, x_2, x_3 are determined from the quasilinear system of first-order equations obtained from (1), (6), and the finite relation $n_1^2 + n_2^2 + n_3^2 = 1$:

$$p_{,i} + n_j n_{i,j} + k n_i n_{,s} = 0, \quad i, j, s = 1, 2, 3; \quad k = \frac{(3\varepsilon + 2m)}{(3\varepsilon - 4m)}. \quad (7)$$

The particle velocity vector for a known stress tensor is determined from the conditions of incompressibility (4) and isotropy (5).

At $m = 0$, the parameter $k = 1$ and system (7) formally coincide with the system of equations of D. D. Ivlev [4] of the Tresca theory of plasticity under the condition of complete plasticity. In this case, the substitution that satisfies condition (2) and relation (3) for $m = 0$ differs from substitution (6).

Analysis of the structure of solutions to system (7) for $k = 1$ applies to the system (7) and for $k \neq 1$. If for $k = 1$ the normals to the characteristic surfaces form a cone with the half-angle $\varphi = \pi/4$ and the axis oriented along the unit eigenvector $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, n_2, n_3)$ of the stress tensor, then for $k \neq 1$ the half-angle $\varphi = \text{arctg}(1/\sqrt{k})$.

The system for determining the velocity vector has a characteristic cone with a half-angle $\varphi = \pi/4$.

Submodels for system (7) with $k \neq 1$ are considered in [5].

System (4), (5), and (7) is hyperbolic. For this system, the problem of the propagation of plastic state zones in an unbounded medium from the boundary of a convex cavity, which is subjected to normal pressure, shear forces, and given displacement velocities, is considered. In [6, 7, 8], for systems (4), (5), (7) with $m = 0$, a numerical method was proposed for solving the Cauchy problem in an orthogonal curvilinear coordinate system (α, θ, γ) formed by rotation around the vertical z axis of a smooth convex curve L with support function $F(\gamma)$ (Fig. 2), where the coordinate surfaces $\alpha = \text{const}$ are equidistant. Taking into account (6), this method can be applied to the solution of the Cauchy problem for systems (4), (5), and (7) with $m \neq 0$.

Figure 2 – Orthogonal curvilinear coordinate system (α, θ, γ) : coordinate surface $S(\alpha = 0)$, basis vectors $k_\alpha, k_\theta, k_\gamma$ and generatrix L of the coordinate surface S

As an example, the problem of the propagation of zones of the plastic state from the boundary of an ellipsoidal cavity formed by rotation around the z axis of a convex curve L with the support function $F(\gamma) = \sqrt{a^2 \sin^2 \gamma + b^2 \cos^2 \gamma}$, where a, b are the semiaxes of the ellipse, were solved.

The problem was solved in dimensionless variables. For $m = 0$, the stresses have the form:

$$\sigma_{\alpha\alpha} = p + n_\alpha^2, \quad \sigma_{\alpha\theta} = n_\alpha n_\theta, \quad \sigma_{\alpha\gamma} = n_\alpha n_\gamma,$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = p + n_\theta^2, \quad \sigma_{\gamma\gamma} = p + n_\gamma^2, \quad \sigma_{\theta\gamma} = n_\theta n_\gamma,$$

where $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}, \sigma_{\alpha\theta}, \sigma_{\alpha\gamma}, \sigma_{\theta\theta}, \sigma_{\gamma\gamma}, \sigma_{\theta\gamma}$ are the stress components in the coordinate system (α, θ, γ) divided by $2k_s \varepsilon$; $p = \sigma / (2k_s \varepsilon) - 1/3$; $n_\alpha, n_\theta, n_\gamma$ are the components of the unit eigenvector corresponding to the principal stress σ_1 . At $m \neq 0$, the stresses were calculated by the formula (6), in which $n_1 = n_\alpha, n_2 = n_\theta, n_3 = n_\gamma$ should be put.

In the numerical solution, the semiaxis of the ellipsoid is $a = 2$, and the semiaxis $b = 1$. At $m = 0$, the following initial conditions were set on the surface of the cavity ($\alpha = 0$): $p(0) = 1, n_\alpha(0) = 1, n_\theta(0) = n_\gamma(0) = 0$. To compare the solutions obtained at $m = 0$ and $m \neq 0$, the initial values for $\xi(0)$ in formulas (6) were chosen so that the normal stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$ at $\alpha = 0$ coincided.

Figure 3 shows the dependences of the stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$ on the coordinate α for the angles $\gamma = 0$ and $\gamma = \pi/2$ at $m = 0$ and $m = 0,5$.

Figure 3 – Distribution of stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$ near an elliptical cavity for angles $\gamma = 0$ and $\gamma = \pi/2$ depending on the coordinate α : dotted lines – $m = 0$, solid lines – $m = 0,5$

Figure 4 – Distribution of stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$, $\sigma_{\gamma\gamma}$ and $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ near the elliptical cavity for the angle $\gamma = \frac{\pi}{4}$ depending on the coordinate α : dotted lines – $m = 0$, solid lines – $m = 0,5$

Figure 4 shows the dependences of the stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}$, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, and $\sigma_{\gamma\gamma}$ on α for $\gamma = \pi/4$ at $m = 0$ and $m = 0,5$.

Thus, under the linear dependence of the yield condition on the average stress for the case of complete plasticity, the Cauchy problem of the propagation of zones of the plastic state in an unbounded medium from the boundary of a convex surface on which normal pressure acts is numerically solved.

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